

Reflection assignments MDPhar

All reflection questions are shown in the context of the different ALACT cycles during the MDPhar course and the associated ALACT phases. For each cycle, the students are asked to answer the reflection questions of that cycle.

Version: June 2022

Presenting

ALACT cycle. phase	Reflection questions in assignment				
1.1 - Act	<i>[Previous learning experience with presenting - prior to course]</i>				
1.2 - Look back	Briefly describe your previous experiences with presenting (in other courses, high school, etc.). How do you experience presenting (fun/exciting/difficult/etc)? What feeling do you get from the idea of making a pitch and doing a scientific presentation within this project?				
1.3 - Analyze/Awareness	<p>What should a presenter do above all to make sure you stay hooked? Name at least 3 aspects and explain why they are important for a good presentation (Now first watch knowledge clips 1, 2, and 3 that accompany the assignment, but also think of good presenters you have seen in action yourself)</p> <p>Also, name at least 3 things that cause you to disengage from a presentation and explain how these aspects can pose a risk to the effectiveness of a presentation</p> <p>What about your presentation skills is already well developed? Support your answer with previous learning experiences, feedback you have received on a presentation, or general feedback you have received from people in the past (e.g., "You are so good at telling how something works in a few minutes").</p> <p>In what area do you see room for improvement regarding your presentation skills? Support this e.g., with concrete previous experience(s), feedback you received on a presentation, or general feedback from people on you as a person (e.g., "You tend to speak rather inaudibly")</p>				
1.4 - Create	<p>In the "Create" phase, you will formulate one or more personal learning goals based on your analysis in the previous question. You will be working on this learning goal when creating your video pitch and preparing your literature presentation. Make sure your learning goal is such that you can practice this in your video pitch and literature presentation. Include the questions you answered above to develop your learning goal(s). Look in the assessment rubric (verbal and nonverbal communication) and the knowledge clips mentioned above for inspiration.</p> <p>To do this well, you need to formulate your learning objective as specific, measurable, actionable, relevant and time-bound (SMART) (see Table 1):</p> <p>Table 1. SMART criteria for establishing a learning objective.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>SMART criteria?</th> <th>Indicator</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Specifically</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concrete and unambiguous description of the goal (what do you want to achieve?) Consists of a verb + Noun. Detail-oriented: for example, what you are going to work on </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	SMART criteria?	Indicator	Specifically	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concrete and unambiguous description of the goal (what do you want to achieve?) Consists of a verb + Noun. Detail-oriented: for example, what you are going to work on
SMART criteria?	Indicator				
Specifically	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concrete and unambiguous description of the goal (what do you want to achieve?) Consists of a verb + Noun. Detail-oriented: for example, what you are going to work on 				

Measurable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear what information is used to achieve the learning objective. Can you "measure" in the video and feedback whether you have achieved your learning objective? • Can be named both quantitatively and qualitatively; for example, 3 positive comments from fellow students
Action-oriented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear how you will achieve the learning goal • Take into account any factors beyond your control
Relevant/Realistic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The learning objective is based on the assessment criteria of the video pitch (e.g., in terms of verbal or nonverbal communication) • It must be achievable in the foreseeable future, so not: "I want to become like Steve Jobs"
Time-bound	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The learning objective specifically indicates when the goal is achieved

Examples of poorly formulated goals:

- "I want to become a better presenter."
- "I want to give a good presentation."
- "I'm going to prepare better."

These are not specific enough, and difficult to measure (because what is "good" or "better"?), and they are not action-oriented. In addition, preparation has more to do with "how" you want to achieve something, and is not a goal in itself.

Example of a SMART learning goal that is specific:

"My goal is to make eye contact with the viewer during my video pitch and literature presentation, I do this by practicing well in advance with looking into the camera during a video recording and practice in front of a few friends. In the video recording and feedback I ask these friends afterwards, I will check if this is indeed the case"

Analyzing this learning objective as an example, we see that it is indeed formulated SMART:

- *Specifically, "making eye contact"*
- *Measurable: It is clear how this can be measured because you can see it in the video, and also feedback is requested from a friend after a live presentation*
- *Action-oriented: "By practicing looking into the camera and looking at people in a live presentation"*
- *Relevant: "Making eye contact fits within the assessment criteria "nonverbal communication"*
- *Time-bound: "during my video pitch and literature presentation"*

QUESTION: Think about what in particular you would like to develop within this course to become a better presenter. Formulate a realistic SMART learning goal, naming specific actions you will do to begin to achieve those goals. The learning goal should flow logically from your analysis in the previous questions and fall within the assessment criteria of presentation skills.

1.5/2.1 - Trial/Act

[preparing and recording the video pitch - Week 1]

<p>2.2 -Look back</p>	<p>What was your personal learning goal for presenting that you prepared in reflection assignment 1? <i>Note: If you received feedback on your learning objective in reflection assignment 1, please provide your improved learning objective here!</i></p> <p>Look back at your pitch one more time. Describe your feelings about the end result of your pitch and explain why. Explain what you liked about the preparation and recording of your pitch? And what was disappointing?</p> <p>To what extent did you stick to your action plan to work on your SMART presentation goal? Did you make any adjustments? Explain how your approach contributed to the end result of your video pitch.</p> <p>What road blocks did you encounter that may have made the pitch preparation/recording go less smoothly than you thought? Explain the causes. <i>For example, think about your behavior or thoughts/feelings during preparation or during the presentation. (e.g. perfectionism, insecurity, thinking too easily about something, procrastinating, etc.).</i></p>
<p>2.3 - Analyze</p>	<p>In reflection assignment 1, you listed 3 things that are necessary for you to stay hooked on someone else's presentation. Now that you have reviewed your video pitch, to what extent do you think your presentation in this video pitch meets these 3 things? Explain!</p> <p>What did you particularly notice in the feedback you received? What are the most important tips and tips? To what extent do you recognize yourself in them?</p> <p>Explain the extent to which you have progressed in working toward your learning goal? Use the following sources of information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The feedback you received • Your own analysis/reflection to previous questions, • e.g. compare your first and last versions of the video pitch: what progress do you see? • How does your pitch compare to those of your group mates?
<p>2.4 - Create</p>	<p>What actions will you take to continue working on your learning goal? What will you focus on for the literature presentation next week? Explain and be as specific as possible!</p>
<p>2.5/3.1 - Trial/Act</p>	<p><i>[preparing presentation and presenting literature study - Week 2-3]</i></p>
<p>3.2 - Look back</p>	<p>Review the recording of the live literature presentation.</p> <p>Describe your feelings about the final outcome of your portion of the literature presentation and explain why. Explain what you liked about the preparation and execution of the presentation? And what was disappointing?</p> <p>To what extent did you stick to your action plan to work on your SMART presentation goal? Did you make any adjustments? Explain how your approach contributed to the end result of your presentation.</p> <p>What road blocks did you encounter that may have made your presentation less easy than you thought? Explain what that was due to. For example, think about your</p>

	behavior or thoughts/feelings during preparation or during the presentation. (e.g. perfectionism, insecurity, thinking too easily about something, procrastinating, etc.).
3.3 - Analyze	<p>In reflection assignment 1, you listed 3 things that are necessary for you to stay hooked on someone else's presentation. Now that you have watched back the video recording of your literature presentation, to what extent do you think your presentation met these 3 things? Explain!</p> <p>You have formed your own image of how your presentation went by your own thoughts/feelings/experience. Explain if and to what extent your image of your own presentation was confirmed or changed after watching back the video recording and the feedback you received.</p> <p>Explain the extent to which you have achieved your learning goal. For example, use the following sources of information as "evidence."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The feedback you received • Your own analysis/reflection to previous questions, • comparison of your video pitch with your video recording of the literature presentation <p>What did you learn about yourself as a presenter through this project? Explain! <i>Also consider eye openers while watching back the presentation recordings and feedback received.</i></p>
3.4 - Create	Explain whether you will keep the same learning goal for the next presentation, possibly in modified form, or whether you will set a new learning objective for yourself.
3.5/4.1 - Trial/Act	<i>[Next presentation]</i>

Teamwork

ALACT cycle.phase	Reflection questions in assignment
1.1 - Act	<i>[Previous learning experience with teamwork - prior to course]</i>
1.2 - Look back	Briefly describe your previous experiences with teamwork (in other courses, non-study-related activities).
1.3 - Analyze/Awareness	<p>Name at least 2 things you think are important in good teamwork and explain why. Use previous experiences with group work as examples to support your answer.</p> <p>Name at least 2 things that can undermine teamwork and explain why. Use previous experiences with group work as examples to support your answer.</p> <p>How do you rate yourself on each competency related to teamwork? Take a look at the competency framework, and fill in how you rate yourself on the different competencies below [Novice, Intermediate, Advanced, Expert].</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual competency • Group competency • Managing group processes • Creating and executing planning • Communication <p>List examples of (sub)competencies that you already do well on. Substantiate this with previous experience(s) and/or feedback you have had from others in a previous collaboration, or general feedback from people on you as a person (e.g., "You connect people by giving everyone room to express their opinions")</p> <p>Where is there room for improvement regarding your teamwork skills? Substantiate with previous experience(s) and/or feedback you've had from others in a previous collaboration, or general feedback from people on you as a person (e.g., "You also tend to do the work of others and not hold them accountable for not doing theirs.")</p>
1.4 - Create	<p>In the "Create" phase, you will formulate one or more personal learning goals based on your previous experience(s) working together and your analysis of what is important for a good collaboration. You will work on this learning goal during the group work in this course. Include your answers to the previous questions in coming up with your learning goal(s).</p> <p>To do this well, you need to formulate your learning objective as specific, measurable, actionable, relevant and time-bound (SMART) (see Table 2):</p>

Table 2. SMART criteria for creating a learning objective:

SMART criteria?	Indicator
Specifically	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concrete description of goal and intended results (what do you want to achieve?) • Consists of a verb + Noun. • Detail-oriented: for example, what you are going to work on
Measurable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear when the goal is reached. • Can be named both quantitatively and qualitatively; for example, 3 positive comments from fellow students
Action-oriented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear how you will achieve the learning objective • Take into account any factors beyond your control
Relevant/Realistic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The learning objective is based on the competency framework of working together (see the box) • It must be achievable in the foreseeable future, so not: "I want to become like Steve Jobs"
Time-bound	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The learning objective specifically indicates when the goal is achieved

Bad example:

I want to get better at planning

Good example:

My goal is to stick to the agreed schedule and make adjustments as needed. I want to do this by making a to-do list for myself each day so that I can cross off the tasks I have done. I will ask for feedback from my groupmates during team meetings as to whether I have done this to the satisfaction of the group.

- *Specifically, "Sticking to schedule"*
- *Measurable: "Did you make a to-do list every day? Do your groupmates think you kept to the schedule? "*
- *Action-oriented: "Making to-do list and asking for feedback"*
- *Relevant: "Planning "*
- *Time-bound: "every day during the course"*

QUESTION: Think about what you would particularly like to develop within the course regarding teamwork competencies. For example, use the learning goal you formulated during the reflection report of the previous Drug Innovation Project in year 1. Formulate a realistic SMART learning goal and name concrete action points in which you describe how you will achieve the goals. The learning goal should follow logically from your analysis of the above and be aimed at one of the (sub)competences from the framework.

<p>2.2 -Look back</p>	<p>What was your personal learning goal for teamwork that you formulated at the beginning of the course? <i>Note: If you received feedback on your learning objective from reflection assignment 1, please provide your improved learning objective here.</i></p> <p>With what feeling do you look back on the teamwork within your group? Explain why. For example, think about unpleasant situations such as not sticking to the plan of action, and also things that went well.</p> <p>Explain how the collaboration contributed to the final result. How did you use each other's qualities?</p> <p>To what extent did you stick to your action plan to work on your personal SMART teamwork learning goal? What road blocks (if any) did you encounter to work on this learning goal and how did you deal with them? For example, think about your behavior or thoughts/feelings while working together. (e.g., perfectionism, insecurity, thinking too easily about something, procrastinating, not keeping appointments, etc.</p>
<p>2.3 - Analyze/awareness</p>	<p>In reflection assignment 2, you mentioned several conditions that you think are essential for good teamwork. To what extent do you feel that your contribution to the teamwork met these conditions? What could you perhaps have done differently?</p> <p>What did you particularly notice in the peer feedback you received? What are the most important tips and tips? And to what extent do you recognize yourself in them?</p> <p>Explain the extent to which you have achieved your learning goal. Use the following sources of information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The peer feedback you received • Your own analysis/reflection to previous questions (and reflection assignment 2) • Your behavior and experience in previous collaborations <p>How do you rate yourself on each competency related to working together? Take a look at the competency rubric and fill in how you rate yourself on the different competencies below [Novice, Intermediate, Advanced, Expert]. N.B. It is not uncommon that a competency has not yet improved and you are still at the same level. So do not feel inconvenienced to fill in the same as you did in reflection assignment 2. Be as honest as possible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual competency • Group competency • Managing group processes • Creating and executing planning • Communication <p>To what extent does your peers' assessment of the levels of your competencies match your own? Explain why or why not.</p> <p>What did you learn about yourself and your role in the teamwork through this project? Explain! <i>TIP: Also consider eye openers from the peer feedback, or unexpected situations and how you handled them</i></p>
<p>2.4 - Create</p>	<p>Explain whether you will keep the same learning goal for the next teamwork opportunity, possibly in modified form, or whether you will set a new learning goal for yourself.</p>

	Formulate your SMART learning goal for the next time you will work together, focusing on what concrete actions you will take to achieve it.
2.5/3.1 - Trial/Act	<i>[Next learning experience with teamwork]</i>

Remark related to publication:

The reflection questions presented here are a translation of the original Dutch version that was used in the MDPhar course.